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A Radio Source-Tracker in Space

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context of the internship

The LESIA (*Laboratoire d'Etude Spatiale et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique*) laboratory is a research department of the *Observatoire de Paris*, which belongs to the PSL (*Paris Science & Lettres*) Research University. Observatoire de Paris is located in three research centers: in the central Paris area (near Denfer-Rochereau, in the historical Paris observatory), in Meudon (south-west suburb of Paris), and in Nançay (*Région Centre*), which is home of one of the largest radio astronomy observatory in the world. The LESIA lab is located in Meudon. The LESIA, also known as UMR-8109, and is associated with CNRS (*Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique*), *Sorbonne Université* and *Université de Paris*.

Its primary roles are: (i) the design and implementation of scientific instrumentation in space and on the ground, (ii) the analysis and interpretation of scientific observations made by use of the produced instruments, and (iii) the development of advanced techniques applied in ground-based instruments and in space instruments. This approach is applied on four main scientific topics: Stellar Physics, High Angular Resolution and Astrophysics, Heliosphere and Astrophysical Plasmas, Planetary Sciences.

The team I work with focuses on the study of astrophysical plasmas and thus works mainly with radio astronomy observations. I worked within a project called NOIRE (Nanosatellite pour un Observatoire Interferométrique Radio dans l'Espace), which is led by LESIA together with other organization like CNES and ONERA.

1.2 The NOIRE project

Nanosatellites are a ground breaking technology enlarging the scope of space projects. Thanks to their low prices, fast development tracks and easy launch, nanosatellites are making space much more affordable. Thus, many students have now been able to work

Figure 1.1: Atmospheric electromagnetic transmittance or opacity (source: Wikipedia)

on a satellite mission in the past decade. The nanosatellite concept not only benefit to students, but it can also be part of major scientific missions. In our case, the NOIRE project is aiming at observing the radio sky at very low frequency using a swarm of nanosatellites orbiting around the moon [1]. Indeed, radio astronomy has seen a lot of improvement during the last decades, which are enabling new types of observations down to very low frequencies. It is, nowadays, in its golden age with the development of the Square Kilometer Array (SKA). However, the radio sky remains unknown at very low frequency in particular because wavelengths cannot propagate through the atmosphere under ~ 10 MHz as shown on figures 1.1 and 2.3. Another issue with using very large wavelength is the aperture size required to achieve a decent angular resolution. Indeed, the angular resolution is given by $\theta = \lambda/D$ where θ is the angular resolution, λ the wavelength and D the aperture size. As an example, for frequency of 1 MHz and a resolution of 1° , the aperture size required is around 35 km.

The atmospheric issue requires space borne measurements (or on the surface of another celestial body), however, current space radio instrumentation are still in the single antenna era. Other techniques have been used to recover angular resolution with simple antennas but real imaging capability requires interferometry, and is thus still out of reach of current space radio instruments.

All in all, a satellite swarm answers both the atmospheric issue and the aperture size issue. Still, various projects similar to NOIRE are in development and are part of an international effort to increase our knowledge, to identify and improve the technologies that will lead us to a future low frequency radio observatory in space. Yet, some of this projects offers different approach or target like SUNRISE that aims to study the sun using a constellation around the Earth [2] or a study from the European Space Agency (ESA) that discusses the perspective of building an interferometer over the moon surface [3].

My personal objective during this internship was to study the feasibility of using the interferometer as a radio source tracker in order to get its overall spatial orientation as a system. The goal behind this study is to assess whether the interferometer can perform a pointing in the sky by itself, using only its own measurements, or whether it requires a help from external capabilities like GNSS (Géolocalisation et Navigation par un Système de Satellites). My objective is detailed in section 3.3.

1.3 Scientific Objectives

A lot of science can be done with sky observation in the low frequency range. The project is still in its early phase of development, and the main concerns are not to make sure the instrument fulfill a list of requirement in order to achieve a specific objective yet. For now the main concern is to make sure that the various pieces of technology to build such an instrument is ready. There are still a few technological locks that need to be broken. Yet, studies on the scientific objectives that can be fulfilled by this interferometer have been conducted. The Table 1.1 lists some of those objectives. It covers topics as wide as cosmology to planetary science, going by stellar physics.

The scientific matrix detailing the instrumental requirements that have to be met for each scientific objectives have been edited. However, none of these objectives have been definitively selected yet, and they might be refined by the scope of what is actually doable. Thus, the specifications for the instrument will evolve alongside the early phases of the project as many variables are still unknown.

Science Topic	Observed Phenomena	Precision
<i>Cosmology and Astrophysics</i>		
Low frequency anisotropy of CMB	21 cm Line redshifted to 5-30 MHz range	
Foreground sources	Extragalactic sources	
Foreground sources	Low frequency sky mapping	1'
Pulsars	Low frequency dispersion of pulsars	
<i>Solar and Stellar Physics</i>		
Solar physics and Space Weather	Radio bursts associated with solar flares, CME and interplanetary shocks	1'
Solar physics and Space Weather	In-situ electrostatic waves	N/A
Solar physics and Space Weather	Quasi thermal noise spectroscopy	N/A
Stellar physics	Stellar radio bursts	
<i>Planetary and Magnetospheric Sciences</i>		
Magnetospheric radio emissions	Terrestrial magnetospheric radio emissions	0.1'
Magnetospheric radio emissions	Jovian magnetospheric radio emissions	1'
Magnetospheric radio emissions	Kronian magnetospheric radio emissions	
Magnetospheric radio emissions	Uranus and Neptune auroral radio emissions	
Magnetospheric radio emissions	Exoplanetary auroral radio emissions	
Planetary atmospheric electricity	Terrestrial lightnings	1'
Planetary atmospheric electricity	Kronian lightnings	1'
Planetary atmospheric electricity	Uranus lightnings	1'
Planetary Radiation Belts	Earth radiation belts	10'
Planetary Radiation Belts	Jupiter radiation belts	10''

Table 1.1: Science Objectives, adapted from [1]

Chapter 2

Presentation of the instrument

2.1 Presentation of the interferometer

The interferometer is composed of swarm of nanosatellites orbiting the Moon. The number of satellite is not fixed yet but is supposed to be around $N_{sat} = 50$ in its final version [1]. An orbit around the moon is considered in order to perform measurements when the Earth is shadowed by the Moon, so that Earth based radio emissions —either Radio Frequency Interferences (RFI), or natural radio emissions, from the Earth’s inner magnetosphere— are blanked.

Measurement Each sensor-node (i.e., a nanosatellite) is composed of three orthogonal electric dipoles (noted h_1, h_2, h_3), which provide a full polarimetric measurement of radio waves. Their physical length is set to ~ 5 m tip-to-tip (see figure 2.1). Each dipole is connected to a low noise amplifier (LNA) directly located at the antenna feed point in order to reduce the impact of local Radio Frequency Interferences (RFI), as displayed on figure 2.2. Each satellite will also be equipped with its own star tracker in order to provide the orientation of its own antennas.

Each measured and amplified electric signal is digitized by a radio receiver in the 1 kHz — 100 MHz band. The three antennas are sampled simultaneously by parallel Analog-to-Digital converters (ADC). The signals received is then decomposed into a set of N_f frequency channels (or “sub-bands”) by digital processing programmed on on-board Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA). A total of $3N_f$ sub-bands are produced by each sensor-node. Figure 2.2 displays the typical measurement chain on a single sensor-node. This flux of raw data is then processed jointly along with the simultaneous data flux coming from other sensor-nodes. Subsequent steps include data buffering, post-processing, beam forming and/or correlations. The computing load to produce the interferometric array response represents a critical design issue for the instrument. Hence, design studies have to be conducted in order to assess if a central unit is necessary (e.g., a mothership), or if the computation can be distributed among

Figure 2.1: Possible design of the satellite’s antennas

the nodes.

Orbitography The satellites will orbit the moon in a swarm pattern. Each node will follow the same orbit and remain close to the other all along the mission. The idea is to get all sensor-node in Earth occultation at the same time. Several orbital options have been studied but have not been further developed. A Lunar equatorial orbit was considered in the frame of this report. The altitude of the orbit is not constrained by the science requirements but might be constrained by the TM/TC (Telemetry and Telecommand) requirements. In a previous study [1], the orbit have been simulated with a semi-major axis of $\simeq 6000$ km with a period of $\simeq 9$ hours. The satellite were randomly set in an initial sphere of 100 km radius. The orbitography concerns (such as the stability or its evolution in time) are not part of this study.

In this study, the same initialization is used for the simulation. However, the dynamic of the swarm have been neglected, which enables to work exclusively with the initial position. For that orbit, the relative motion between the nodes is slow < 2 m/s, which represents a displacement of 2 m for a snapshot duration of 1 s. This displacement leads to an angular error of $\sim 0.002^\circ$ for a distance of $100km$.

The measurement requirements do not impose any attitude control for each node, however ancillary requirements may impose attitude control, e.g., solar pointing for solar panel, or Earth pointing for ground transmissions. Also, there is a need for attitude control after the initial deployment to damp down the deployment-induced rotation. Beyond this requirements, a low control philosophy is adopted. The natural orbital evolution of the swarm is used instead of trying to strictly control and enforce its shape and the location of each of its nodes. Thus, the overall topology of the swarm

Figure 2.2: Typical architecture for the acquisition and processing on a node. The measurement chain is composed of an antenna, a low noise amplifier (LNA) and a digitization front-end (filtering and conversion). The radio receiver (Rx board) is composed of those front-ends and an FPGA, which extracts N_f sub-bands using polyphase filter banks (PFB) or impulse response filters (IRF). The data stream is sent to the digital processing unit (DPU), which manages all further processing. The data stream is also transmitted. (source: [1])

is not meant to adapt itself for the observations. Hence, it can be considered random for the simulations.

In the frame of this report, the position of the satellite are denoted as \vec{X}_i where the subscript $i \in \{0, \dots, N_{sat}\}$ refers to the satellite number. The distance between a pair of satellites is called the “baseline” and is denoted as $\vec{b}_{i,j} = \vec{X}_i - \vec{X}_j$. N^2 baselines can be formed. However, N of these baselines are $\vec{0}$ and half of the remaining baselines are just the opposite of the other half $\vec{b}_{i,j} = -\vec{b}_{j,i}$. Hence, there are only $N_{bl} = N(N - 1)/2$ independent baselines.

2.2 Environment

Although, the sky remains mostly unknown at very low frequency, it is possible to make an approximated map by extrapolating from the sky maps at higher frequencies. Indeed, most of the phenomena causing the emission at low frequencies covers a large range in the spectra and extend to lower frequency. The lowest frequencies for which the sky has been mapped are around 10 – 50 MHz. Furthermore, the brightness of the sources is assumed to decrease with the frequency. It can be approximated with a power law $(1/\nu^n)$ [4] [5] in the frequency range considered. Although this power law is yet to be estimated, we supposed that it will be measured thanks to demonstration mission and also during the first campaign of measurement with the interferometer. This means that, if the brightness of the main sources is measured at a given frequency, they can be extrapolate for other frequencies within the range.

The spectra of the main sources at very low frequency is shown on figure 2.3. When near the moon, the main source of radio emissions are expected to be the Earth auroral emissions. That is the reason why the interferometer performs its measurement on the far side of the moon in order to get rid of this signal. Aside from the Earth, other planetary emission are expected from Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune. However, these emissions remain less intense than the galactic background. The main concern here, is the variation of activity of both the Sun and Jupiter. Indeed, the Sun periodically goes through and active state where it emits radio waves, and it is similar for Jupiter. Moreover, when a solar burst happens on the surface of the Sun, powerful radio waves are emitted. These emissions are problematic because they cannot be anticipated by space whether contrary to its activity periods. Thus, it should be taken in account in the measurements afterwards.

Aside from the solar system, the sky at low frequency is dominated by four main sources: Cassiopeia A, Cygnus A, Taurus A and Virgo A , see table 2.1. These sources, named the A-team, can play the role of lighthouses for the interferometer.

Source name	Coordinates		Flux density (Jy)		Size (arcmin)
	RA (J2000)	DEC (J2000)	@ 50 MHz	@ 150 MHz	
Cassiopeia A	23h 23m 27.94s	+58°48'42.4"	27104	9856	7.4
Cygnus A	19h 59m 28.35s	+40°44'02.1"	22146	10713	2.3
Taurus A	05h 34m 31.97s	+22°00'52.1"	2008	1368	7.9
Virgo A	12h 30m 49.42s	+12°23'28.0"	2635	1209	15.

Table 2.1: The A-team: coordinates, flux densities, and sizes

Figure 2.3: The radio component spectra observed from Earth, including solar radio emissions, earth and planetary auroral and atmospheric radio emissions, galactic emission and local plasma noise on the antenna (source: [1])

2.3 Work hypothesis

In the case of this study, a series of assumptions have been made:

- the swarm to be static which means that the topology of the swarm remains unchanged, but also that the nodes have no spin. It also implies that the Doppler effect is not considered. Indeed, its effect can be neglected but also it can be compensated if needed.
- the antennas are omni-directional. As the three antennas are the same and in orthogonal directions, they recover the full polarimetric radio waves in every direction. Thus, together, they cover the full sky as an omni-directional antenna. Moreover, the antennas were supposed to function as a short dipole. This assumption is relevant for $\lambda/l_{ant} \ll 1$. With an antenna length of $l_{ant} \simeq 5m$, this assumption can be used up to $\sim 1MHz$. Also, This hypothesis means that the polarization does not matter in the measurements.
- the sub-bands width is yet to be defined in regards to the scientific objectives retained. However, for the purpose of this study, the sub-bands will be considered thin enough in order to suppose the influence of the frequency range to be negligible.
- this first estimation also assumes that: the clocks have no bias; there is no significant multipaths propagation; all sources are in the far field and have no polarization.

Chapter 3

A radio source tracker

3.1 Principle

In order to provide pointing capabilities, the interferometer must have a knowledge of its overall orientation as a system in an absolute inertial frame. Various options can solve the orientation issue and many of them has yet to be studied. In this report, It has been chosen to focus on a solution that can be performed without using interaction with anything else than the satellites of the swarm. This prevents from using a system such as a GNSS for localization, or adding an extra reference point. The main idea behind the algorithm presented in this report is to use the imaging capability of the interferometer in order to function the same way a star-tracker would. In that sense, let's first explain how a classical star-tracker works.

A classical star-tracker is composed of a camera attached to its satellite and comes with a set of algorithms. It has two main modes. The first one is named Lost In Space (LIS). In this mode, the star tracker lists the position of the stars present inside its field of view. These positions are measured using techniques such as the barycenter that gives a sub-pixel precision. Then, it analyzes the pattern of theses stars and compares it to a catalog of star stored in its memory. An algorithm will look for a match between the pattern formed with the stars measured and the patterns from the catalog. Once the match is found, the star-tracker knows in which direction it is looking to and thus, knows the orientation of the satellite on which it is integrated. Then, the star tracker switches to its second mode: Tracking. In this mode, the star tracker follows the position of the stars in its field of view for each time step, thanks to its previous knowledge on their positions. The orientation vector is updated using the shift in positions of the stars between each time step.

In the case of our radio star-tracker the principle is the same except that the image of the sky is not the result of a direct measurement but has to be computed using the signals from every satellites. In addition, the satellites antennas aren't restricted to a field of view and are receiving signal from the whole sky, thus, only the brightest

sources can be used to perform the pattern matching. Thereby, in LIS mode, the radio star-tracker will have to image the whole sky in order to look for the brightest sources. However, when in tracking mode, the radio star-tracker can compute the image only in the region where those sources are expected to be found in order to reduce the computation time.

3.2 Function Analysis

In order to provide a measurement in a specific direction, the interferometer has to point toward this direction. Since the field of view of each antenna is the full sky, a low frequency radio interferometer can not be pointed mechanically, as an optical telescope would. Instead, a specific delay is applied to each node of the array according to the distance between the nodes in that direction. This delay is expressed as a phase shift written $\Delta\phi_i$. Thus, the main function that provides a pointing aims to return a list of phase shifts. This is formalized through the SADT diagram (Structured Analysis and Design Technique) in figure 3.1. In order to compute these phase shifts, one the relative distances between the satellites, also called baselines $\vec{b}_{i,j}$ must be known. However, this information cannot be the result of a direct measure. Indeed, the frame in which the baselines are measured is generally not the same as the frame, in which the pointing direction is requested. This means that the relation between these two frames must also be known. The frame of the pointing direction will be named the *absolute frame* \mathcal{R}_a , it corresponds to the J2000 inertial frame used in astronomy. The frame in which the baselines are computed at first will be named the *system frame* \mathcal{R}_s . Since only the relative distances matter inside the frame, the location of the origin of both frames is not important, only their orientation is of interest. Hence, pointing the interferometer comes down to finding the rotation transform between \mathcal{R}_a and \mathcal{R}_s . This rotation is written as $\vec{Q}_{\mathcal{R}_s/\mathcal{R}_a}$ and can either be expressed as a quaternion or a rotation matrix. This is explained in the SADT diagram that details the function A0 in figure 3.2. The function A1.3 goal is to take as input the previous quaternion and the pointing direction \vec{R}_k and compute the phase shifts.

Nevertheless, the baselines have to be known in the first place. Here, there are two scenarii similar to those of a star tracker. First, the interferometer has no information on its position. This state is known as LIS (Lost In Space) and the instrument has to retrieve pieces of information using the sky. Second, the instrument has a knowledge of his previous orientation or position and can use this information to get its current status more easily than when in LIS. It can for example track a reference point or use propagation equations to make a prediction. It can also combined both a measurement and a prediction using a Kalman Filter in order to increase the accuracy of its prediction. This study focuses on the first scenario where the interferometer is in LIS.

In order to compute the baselines when the interferometer is in LIS, the satellites

first measure their relative distances using, e.g., a TOA-CDMA technique (Time Of Arrival - Code Division Multiple Access), inter-satellites ranging could be precisely determined. However, only the lengths of the baselines $D_{i,j} = \|\vec{b}_{i,j}\|$ is determined that way. At this point, we assume that we have an algorithm that can reconstruct the 3D topology of the swarm using only this information. This function is referred as the function A1.1 on the diagram in figure 3.2. This function will require to construct a frame in which the positions \vec{X}_i can be expressed which is the system frame \mathcal{R}_s .

3.3 Selected approach

The remaining step is the A1.2 function, which goal is to compute the linear transform (rotation) between the 2 frames. The goal of this work was to qualify the capability of the interferometer to achieve this function. The idea was to explore multiple possibilities that can perform this function and to give a first estimate of the precision that can be achieved in the current state of the project. The knowledge of that precision might impact the scientific objectives that will be retained for the future of the project. At the same time, I was in charged of building tools that enables the instrument to generate images that will be useful in various aspects of the project.

The A1.2 function can be implemented with multiple approaches. The main approach considered through this study is depicted on the figure 3.3. The idea is to first compute the correlation between the signals $A_i(t)$ in order to work with the interferometric visibilities $\mathcal{V}_{i,j}$. This processing will be explained in chapter 6. Then, several algorithms exist allowing to generate an image from the visibilities. Some of them are explored in chapter 4. This first step will be referred to as the first part of the pipeline.

At this point, several options exist to compare the measured sky to the catalog. For instance, it is possible to generate a reference image from the sky model and the ephemeris and then compute the correlation between the two images. However, this approach was discarded because the correlation is highly influenced by the few brightest sources and is very sensitive to the presence of other emitting bodies and background emissions. The approach chosen is closer that of the classical star-tracker. It generates a list of positions of the brightest bodies for both the measured image and the sky model in order to highlight the pattern formed by the sources rather than their intensities. This last steps will be referred to as the second part of the pipeline and will be detailed in chapter 5.

Figure 3.1: Main function A0

Figure 3.2: Description of the function A0

Figure 3.3: Description of function A1.2

Chapter 4

Image generation methods

As explained in the previous section, the radio star-tracker requires the capability to generate an image of the whole sky. Developing such algorithms is not only useful for getting the orientation but also starts the development for the main use of the interferometer, which requires to compute images. In that sense, various approaches have been drafted in order to try and compare them.

Let's first give a few notion on how an interferometer works. The signals received by a pair of antennas located on two sensor-nodes can be used together to get more information than both signals taken alone. For instance, they can be correlated or summed together. However, the signals have to be coherent in time, which means they were acquired while receiving the same wavefront coming from the same source. Due to the relative location of the antennas, the “radio” optical path must be taken into account. This is explained in 2D on figure 4.1. For two antennas separated by a distance $\|\vec{b}\|$ receiving a wavefront coming a direction \vec{s} with an angle θ , the signal have to travel a greater distance to reach the second antenna than the first one. This difference of distance $d = \vec{b} \cdot \vec{s} = \|\vec{b}\|\cos(\theta)$ correspond to a time delay $\tau_g = d/c$ where c is the speed of light. Thus, for a given frequency ν , this delay can be expressed as a phase shift $\Delta\phi = 2\pi\nu/\tau_g = 2\pi d/\lambda$ with $\lambda = c/\nu$ the wavelength.

Later on, the formulas use the wavevector $\vec{k} = 2\pi\vec{s}/\lambda$. Finally, when using the complex notation, applying a phase shift is equivalent to multiplying by $\exp(-i_c\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b})$ where i_c is the imaginary unit.

The source brightnesses B are expressed in Jansky ($1 \text{ Jy} = 10^{-26} \text{ W/m}^2/\text{Hz}$). On the other hand, the antennas measure a signal proportional to the electric field E of the incoming waves. It verifies $B \propto E^2$. Then, when reconstructing an image, interferometric maps are measured in brightness units I of Jy/beam, where “beam” is a nominal area over which the brightness is defined.

For the following sections, the satellites are supposed to act like isotropic antennas. The i -th satellite measure a signal proportional to:

Figure 4.1: Simplified schematic diagram of a two-element interferometer (source: [6])

$$A_{\nu,i}(t) = \iint \mathcal{A}(\Omega_k) E_\nu(\Omega_k, t) \exp(-i_c \vec{k} \cdot \vec{X}_i) d\Omega_k \quad (4.1)$$

where $\Omega_k = (\theta_k, \phi_k)$ are the angular component of \vec{k} on the sphere, \mathcal{A} is the antenna response and E_ν is the electric field at the frequency ν coming from the direction \vec{k} .

For this part, I will only consider the satellite to act as a single isotropic antenna. Hence, $\forall \vec{k}$, $\mathcal{A}(\Omega_k) = 1$. Also, only a single sub-band is considered and is supposed to be thin enough to consider the wavevector k to be constant. So the subscripts \bullet_ν is removed.

In the case of a sky composed exclusively of point sources of electric field E_s and in the direction \vec{k}_s , this formula comes down to

$$A_i(t) = \sum_{source\ s} E_s(t) \cdot \exp(-i_c \vec{k}_s \cdot \vec{X}_i) \quad (4.2)$$

4.1 Coherent sum

This method is the easiest to implement and can even be done analogically for a ground-based interferometer. The idea is to sum up all the signal after applying a well chosen delay. The delay is chosen accordingly to the pointing direction in order to create a constructive interference in that direction.

$$I(\theta, \phi) = \Re \left\langle \left\| \sum_i A_i \exp(i_c \vec{k}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \vec{X}_i) \right\|^2 \right\rangle \quad (4.3)$$

where A_i is the signal measured by the i -th satellite, i_c is the imaginary unit, λ the frequency, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the time average, \Re denotes the real part and $\|\cdot\|^2$ is computed using $(\cdot)(\cdot)^*$.

This method has the main advantage to be really simple and can easily be implemented on the interferometer. Indeed, each satellite can compute a map of phase shift and apply it to its measurements. Then, the only operation left is to gather the signal from the sensor-nodes and sum them up.

In terms of computation complexity, this method requires to add a phase shift for every pixel (N_{pix}) and for every antenna. This means that the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N_{sat} N_{pix})$.

The main drawback of this method is the quality of the images, but this aspect will be discussed later in the result chapter.

4.2 Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT)

One of the main interest in using an antenna array is to work with the correlations between the signals of the antennas. A correlation between two antenna is called a visibility and is expressed as $\mathcal{V}_{i,j} = \langle A_i \cdot A_j^* \rangle$. Thus,

$$\mathcal{V}_{i,j} = \iint B(\Omega_k) \exp(-i_c \vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}_{i,j}) d\Omega_k \quad (4.4)$$

and for point sources only:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_{i,j} &= \left\langle \left(\sum_s E_s(t) \cdot \exp(-i_c \vec{k}_s \cdot \vec{X}_i) \right) \cdot \left(\sum_s E_s(t) \cdot \exp(-i_c \vec{k}_s \cdot \vec{X}_j) \right)^* \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \sum_{s_1} \sum_{s_2} E_{s_1}(t) \cdot E_{s_2}^*(t) \cdot \exp\left(-i_c((\vec{k}_{s_1} \cdot \vec{X}_i) - (\vec{k}_{s_2} \cdot \vec{X}_j))\right) \right\rangle \\ &= \sum_{s_1} \sum_{s_2} E_{s_1}(t) \cdot E_{s_2}^*(t) \cdot \exp\left(-i_c((\vec{k}_{s_1} \cdot \vec{X}_i) - (\vec{k}_{s_2} \cdot \vec{X}_j))\right) \delta(s_1 - s_2) \quad (4.5) \\ &= \sum_s \|E_s\|^2 \exp\left(-i_c \vec{k}_s \cdot (\vec{X}_i - \vec{X}_j)\right) \\ &= \sum_s \|E_s\|^2 \exp(-i_c \vec{k}_s \cdot \vec{b}_{i,j}) \end{aligned}$$

One of the main advantages of this method is that the time average over the correlations enables to remove the cross product of the signal coming from different sources. In the end, the correlation can be expressed as a linear combination of every point sources, which enables to treat each point source individually.

The dot product in the exponential can be developed using

$$\vec{k}_s = 2\pi \begin{bmatrix} l \\ m \\ n \end{bmatrix} \quad b_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

with $n = \pm\sqrt{1 - l^2 - m^2}$ because $\|\vec{s}\| = 1$.

Then, equation 4.4 becomes:

$$\mathcal{V}(u, v, w) = \iint \|E(l, m)\|^2 \exp(-2i_c\pi(ul + vm + wn)) \frac{dl dm}{n} \quad (4.7)$$

which looks like a Fourier Transform for a given set of u, v, w . Hence, each visibility measurement gives a the value of a point in the Fourier space, also called the UV-space in interferometry. If the UV-space is fully known, one can get the brightness $B(l, m)$ by running an inverse Fourier transform. In practice, the UV-space is never fully known but only a few points are measured, one point for each independent baseline. Let's note that if the observed sky remains constant in time, it is possible to gather visibilities measured at different time in order to fill in a greater portion of the UV-space. However, in the case of a snapshot, only the measurement at a given time can be used which is the case here. In order to compute the image of the sky using a discrete set of visibilities, one can use the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) that is expressed as followed:

$$I(\theta, \phi) = \Re\left(\frac{1}{N_{bl}} \sum_{(i,j)} \mathcal{V}_{i,j} \exp(+i_c\vec{k}(\theta, \phi) \cdot b_{i,j})\right) \quad (4.8)$$

In terms of computation complexity, this method requires to compute a phase shift for every pixel and for every baselines. Thus the time complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N_{sat}^2 N_{pix})$ which is significantly more than the coherent sum. However, this calculus can be highly parallelized and on-board computer optimized for that kind of computation already exist.

4.3 Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

This method is similar to the previous one but takes advantage of fast computation process of the Fast Fourier Transform. The basic working is to break up a transform of length N into two transforms of length $N/2$. However, in order to perform the FFT, one has to work with a regular grid.

2D - Most of the time this method is implemented in 2 dimension. This means that the whole celestial sphere cannot be computed at once using this method, but only a small portion, in which the sphere is considered as sufficiently flat.

In terms of calculus, if one takes the equation 4.7, suppose $l \ll 1$, $m \ll 1$ - thus $n \simeq 1$ - and multiply both side by $\exp(2i_c\pi w)$, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}(u, v)e^{2i_c\pi w} &= \iint \|E(l, m)\|^2 \exp(-2i_c\pi(ul + vm)) dl dm \\ &\propto \mathcal{F}\{B(l, m)\}(u, v) \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

Hence, the image can be retrieve by running the inverse FFT:

$$B(l, m) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\mathcal{V}'(u, v)\}(l, m) \quad (4.10)$$

where $\mathcal{V}'(u, v) = \mathcal{V}(u, v)e^{2i_c\pi w}$ is the grid of visibilities. In order to compute this grid, one has to calculate the projection of the baselines in both the pointing direction which gives w and on the orthogonal plan which gives (u, v) . Then, (u, v) coordinates have to be placed on a regular grid. For this last step several gridding and weighting functions exist and will not be explored in the scope of this report.

The main advantage of the FFT relies in its computation complexity. For an image of N_{pix} total pixel, the image is processed with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N_{pix}\log(N_{pix}))$. The computation complexity no longer depends on the number of satellites or baseline because each visibility measurement is gather in a regular grid. However, that also means that each visibility $\mathcal{V}(u, v)$ are set on the grid to (u, v) values that differ a bit from the original value $\mathcal{V}(u_k = i\Delta u, v_k = j\Delta v)$. Several solutions have been found to address this issue, but still imperfections remain.

3D - Although this method is mostly unknown, it may have some use for this interferometer. Indeed, the FFT algorithm can be run with a 3D regular grid. When doing so the equation describing the describing the transformation becomes:

$$B(l, m) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\mathcal{V}(u, v, w)\}(l, m, n)\sqrt{1 - l^2 - m^2}\delta(n \pm (1 - l^2 - m^2)) \quad (4.11)$$

The calculus behind is described in the appendix A. According to this equation, the brightness of the celestial sphere can be found where $n = \pm\sqrt{1 - l^2 - m^2}$, which is on the sphere inside the 3D grid, see Figure 4.2.

Thus, if the grid is a cube of N_{grid} elements per side and the image is compose of N_{pix} elements of the same size, it means that $N_{pix} \simeq \pi N_{grid}^2$. Hence, there are a large majority of elements of the grid that will be calculated for nothing because they are not physically meaningful.

As the voxels of the grid do not perfectly match the pixels of the output image, it was necessary to implement a function that makes the link between the two. This function takes the angular coordinates of each pixel of the output image, then finds the position of the point on the sphere corresponding to that direction inside the 3D grid and then

Figure 4.2: Schematic view of the 3D grid after the inverse Fourier Transform. The 3 axes correspond to (l,m,n)

gets the closest voxels. The value given to that pixel is a weighted average of those voxels. More precisely, I used a $3*3*3$ kernel filled with weights calculated accordingly to the distance to the reference point. This function might be too complicated for what it does but further experiments have to be performed in order to quantify the benefit of this approach. Also, the weights to use are still in development. The results from this method are not presented in this report.

Another issue raised by this method is the periodicity of the FFT, it makes the 3D-grid to be periodical. The problem is that if there is a source close to the north pole of the celestial sphere and thus close to the upper edge of the grid, this source also impacts the under edge of the grid and thereby a source might be noticed in the south pole of the celestial sphere although no source is here.

In the same way as in 2D, once the visibilities are placed on the grid, the algorithm runs efficiently. The computation complexity is:

$$\mathcal{O}(N_{grid}^3 \log(N_{grid}^3)) \simeq \mathcal{O}((N_{pix}/\pi)^{3/2} \log((N_{pix}/\pi)^{3/2})).$$

4.4 Spherical Wave Harmonic Transform (SWHT)

The Spherical Wave Harmonic Transform has been expressed and developed by T.D. Carozzi and his team [7] [8]. This method enables to image the full celestial sphere at once by decomposing the visibilities over spherical harmonic components. The equations behind this method are the following:

$$B(\theta, \phi) = \sum_{l=0}^{l_{max}} \sum_{m=-l}^{m=+l} b_{lm} Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi) \quad (4.12)$$

$$b_{lm} = \frac{2k}{4\pi^2(-i_c)^l} \sum_{(i,j)}^{N_{bl}} \mathcal{V}_{i,j} j_l(kr_{i,j}) Y_{lm}^*(\theta_{i,j}, \phi_{i,j}) \quad (4.13)$$

where Y_{lm} is the standard, orthonormal spherical harmonic function with l, m corresponding to the polar and azimuthal quantal numbers respectively, and j_l is the spherical Bessel function of the first kind. b_{lm} are the multipole moments of the sky and $(r_{i,j}, \theta_{i,j}, \phi_{i,j})$ are the spherical coordinates of the baseline $\vec{b}_{i,j}$.

In order to use this method, one first has to compute the b_{lm} coefficient which is basically a sum over the visibilities. Then, one has to sum these coefficients for every quantal numbers. It is numerically not possible to compute the infinite number of quantal number. Here, it was chosen to select a maximum polar number l_{max} and only the harmonic below this value will be considered. The higher the polar number, the smaller the scale of variation in the harmonic. Thus, the threshold can be chosen accordingly to the resolution of the interferometer given the frequency. The scale of variation in the spherical harmonic is π/l_{max} and this scale has to be chosen 2 to 5 times smaller than the expected resolution, this factor is called f later on. For example, to get a resolution of 1° , one has to use $l_{max} > 180.f$ The number elements to compute are then $N_{elem/pix} = (l_{max} + 1)(l_{max} + 2)/2 N_{bl}$ for every pixel of the image.

For an image of the whole celestial sphere with N_{pix} , the resolution has to be $res = \sqrt{4\pi/N_{pix}}$. Or $res = \pi/(fl_{max})$, so $l_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4} N_{pix}/f^2}$. Hence, the number of element to compute for each pixel is $N_{elem/pix} \propto N_{pix} N_{bl}$. All in all, the computational complexity of this method is $\mathcal{O}(N_{sat}^2 N_{pix}^2)$.

Although the complexity of this method is significantly worst than the previous ones, it can provide information on the spherical harmonic coefficient which are more relevant for the study of the Dark Ages for example.

Chapter 5

Coordinates retrieving

In order to retrieve the rotation matrix between the system frame and the absolute frame, the radio source tracker requires to compare the positions of a few reference sources. For that purpose, the instrument has to be able to find the positions of those sources in the system frame, to identify them and compare them to their positions in the absolute frame. Thus, this algorithm works as followed: first, find the sources coordinates then find to which source from the catalog they correspond and finally find the rotation matrix between the coordinates.

5.1 Finding the sources

The more sources can be used to retrieve the rotation, the better the precision. Thus, one should look for a way to find as much sources as possible. However, as mentioned earlier, the sky at low-frequencies is dominated by the A-team which are only four. This means that those four sources are somehow easier to find but overshadow the other ones. Even though, four points can be enough to compute the rotation, it can be complicated to get the coordinates of these sources. Indeed, two of them are 10 times brighter than the two others. Also, other sources can appear during the observation like the Sun or Jupiter, whose radio emissions are sporadic and can be very intense.

Is it important to notice here that the point spread function (PSF) of an interferometer is very different from the PSF of an optical telescope. For a fixed phase shift toward the pointing direction, there can be other directions in which some antennas are in constructive interferences even though there are no sources in this direction. These are called the grating lobes. This means that the signal from one source impact the measured signal in all direction accordingly to the geometry of the swarm. That is why the PSF of a bright celestial body may have an amplitude variation greater than the signal from fainter sources well separated.

Thus, in most cases, it is not possible to find directly the coordinates of multiple sources using the reconstructed image without any processing. That is why the images

have to be cleaned in order to find dimmer sources. For that purpose, I choose to run a deconvolution algorithm that runs as follow: find the brightest source and its amplitude, store its position in a list, simulate its signal on the antennas, subtract it to the visibilities, generate a new image without this source and iterates. This algorithm requires to reconstruct multiple images and cannot be parallelized. This is the limiting factor in terms of computation time and may be improved in further updates.

For each iteration the deconvolution algorithm requires to find the position of the source with great precision for the source subtraction to be efficient. For that purpose, a two step search was adopted. A first image is computed at very low frequency in order to look for the hot spots and select the brightest pixel of that map. Then, another image is computed with higher frequency and resolution but only in the area around the hot pixel of the previous step. It is normalized between 0 and 1 and then a 2D-Gaussian function is fitted in this image as shown on figure 5.1. This function enables to know the sources position as well as its amplitude and size. Moreover, thanks to the fact that the source covers multiple pixel, the Gaussian fit gives an accuracy on the source position better than the imaging resolution.

However, the hot spot might not correspond to a source but to a feature of the galactic background, for instance. The point is that, it is important for the rest of the pipeline to make sure the result from the fitting is actually a point source. To sort the result, a criteria that tells if the source found can be accepted was implemented. This criteria relies on three parameters, the signal to noise ratio (SNR), the angular size and the average difference between the image and the Gaussian fitted as followed:

- SNR: $> 1\%$
- angular size: half the resolution
- error of the fit: $< 1\%$

Afterwards, the resulting position is stored in a list and its parameters are used to simulate the signal received by every antenna — as so the visibilities — generated by this source . It is then subtracted to the visibilities measured for both frequencies used to compute the images. Although the amplitude of the source is not the same for the two frequencies, I supposed the amplitude at the lower frequency can be approximated using a model or the amplitude measured on its map.

If the Gaussian fit ends up into an area where no source is found, a mask is applied around this area to prevent the next step to reach the same place. This is a limitation because the background signal coming from other sources than the bright point sources is not subtracted and, thus, the fainter sources remains undetectable.

The deconvolution algorithm runs over 10 to 20 iterations. Afterwards, the remaining signal can reconstruct a cleaned image in which the main sources have been removed. This is highlighted on figure 5.2 where almost only the galaxy can be seen on the cleaned image.

Figure 5.1: Normalized image at higher resolution with Gaussian fit

Figure 5.2: Image reconstruct by DFT before (left) and after (right) deconvolution (the scale of the color bar is different)

5.2 Pattern Matching

Once, the algorithm has found the main sources of the sky, it has to compare them to the catalog of known sources. The goal is to give a correspondence to each object found. For example “source found number 2 is Centaurus alpha”. In order to do so, the algorithm developed here is very similar to the ones used in classical star tracker. The only differences are that the field of view is much larger and the number of sources found can be low.

The idea is to generate a table of relationship between the star, one for the catalog T_{cat} and one for the measured sources T_{mes} , and to compare them. The tables are composed of information about every triangle of sources that can be formed using the sources. For every triangle, the table references the angular distance between the main star and the two other, plus the bi-angle in between (α, β, γ) as represented in figure 5.3. The same table entries were used in [9]. The bi-angle γ is calculated as followed:

$$\cos(\gamma) = \cos(c) - \frac{\cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta)}{\sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta)} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.3: The Parameters Used to Characterize a Star

Other table entries can be used for the tables but have not been tested yet. The objective of the pattern match is just to make a match with the catalog so as long as the match is correct, it does not affect the precision of the star tracker. That is why its improvement can be delayed for now.

One can notice that using every triangle possible may lead to very long table. For instance, if the catalog contain N_{scat} sources, its table has a dimension of $N_{scat} \cdot (N_{scat} -$

1).($N_{scat} - 2$) * 3. However, three points are enough to compute the rotation. Still, the higher the number of point, the greater the precision over the rotation. According to the simulations, the number of found sources is usually around 3 and 20, which generates a table of relatively low length for computer capability. As the interferometer mainly finds the brightest sources, it is not necessary to use the whole catalog. Instead, only the brightest can be used to build the table. In my algorithm I use the first 10 brightest sources if the number of found sources is lower than 6 and if it is higher, 2 times the number of found sources because I expect the algorithm to miss no more than half of the catalog sources when sorted by brightness.

Once the two tables are established, for each element of the first table, the algorithm compute the absolute difference between this element and every other element of the second table. It creates a greater table T_{diff} of shape $N_{scat} \cdot (N_{scat} - 1) \cdot (N_{scat} - 2) * N_{smes} \cdot (N_{smes} - 1) \cdot (N_{smes} - 2) * 3$. Then, the algorithm looks for the triangle that looks the same. For that purpose, a threshold is applied for every entries of the triangle, if the three parameters of the difference between the triangle is lower than their threshold, the couple of triangle is validated. The other way around, if only one of the parameters is higher than the threshold, the couple of triangle is not validated.

For the angular distances, the threshold used is 2 times the angular resolution at the frequency used to fit the sources position. For the bi-angle, threshold used is 2 times the previous threshold.

At this point, a voting method was implemented to perform the match. For each found source, the algorithm counts the number of validated triangle formed with this source and one from the catalog. Thus, by looking at the source from the catalog that share the greatest number of validated triangle, one can know to which source from the catalog the source found correspond. It comes down to a permutation matrix. Finally, the only thing left to do is to sort and crop the lists of source in order for the indices to match for the next step.

One important thing to notice is the need for the rejection of error. Indeed, the interferometer might find sources in places where there are not, which are called false-detection. As well, a few sources from the catalog might not be found by the interferometer. It implies from the algorithm to be able to detect the source that does not have a corresponding source in the other table. For that, I implemented a minimum threshold over the number of vote per couple of sources. This threshold is expressed as $(N_{smes} - 1) \cdot (N_{smes} - 2) / 2$, Which is to say that each true positive should be able to complete validated triangles with at least half of the other measured sources. This means that at least half of the sources found are true positive. If less than three matches are found, the measurement of the orientation is consider to be a failure and has to be run again with new measurements.

Figure 5.4: (a) is the Boolean table of T_{diff} after application of the thresholds, For (b) and (c), the columns correspond to the measured sources number and the lines correspond to the catalog sources number. (b) counts the number of vote and (c) is the final permutation matrix

5.3 Rotation matrix

The output of the radio star-tracker is a rotation that expresses the link between the system frame and the absolute frame in which the position of the star is studied. This rotation can either be expressed as a matrix or a quaternion $\mathbf{M}_{Rs/Ra}$. Once the two lists of sources are cropped and sorted as mentioned in the previous section, they can be compared. Let \vec{P}_{cati} and \vec{P}_{mes_i} be the position of the source i in respectively the catalog and the measurement list. The rotation matrix should verify

$$\forall i \quad \vec{P}_{cati} = \mathbf{M}_{rot} \cdot \vec{P}_{mes_i}$$

Let $\vec{X}_{i/Ra}$ and $\vec{X}_{i/Rs}$ be the position of the source i in respectively the absolute frame and the system frame. The rotation matrix verify

$$\forall i \quad \vec{X}_{i/Ra} = \mathbf{M}_{Rs/Ra} \cdot \vec{X}_{i/Rs}$$

Let $\vec{X}_{i,mes}$ be measured position of the source i . It can be expressed as

$$\vec{X}_{i,mes} = \vec{X}_{i/Rs} + \vec{\epsilon}_i$$

where $\vec{\epsilon}$ is error on the measurement. Then,

$$\forall i \quad \vec{X}_{i/Ra} - \mathbf{M}_{Rs/Ra} \cdot \vec{X}_{i,mes} = \vec{\epsilon}'_i \quad (5.2)$$

with $\vec{\epsilon}'_i = \mathbf{M}_{Rs/Ra} \cdot \vec{\epsilon}_i$

Thus in order to get $\mathbf{M}_{Rs/Ra}$, the idea is to find the matrix that minimize the term on the left in the previous equation 5.2. For that, a least square minimization was implemented.

Figure 5.5: Position of sources on the celestial sphere. The black crosses are the positions in the catalog, the blue crosses are the measured positions and the red crosses are the measured position after applying the computed rotation matrix

Chapter 6

Simulation

6.1 Instrument simulation

In order to simulate the instrument, the pipeline first setup the positions of the satellites. For that, I used an uniform distribution of $N_{sat} = 50$ inside a sphere of radius $D_{max} = 100km$. These positions are expressed in the system frame. Different function were implemented to run the setup with different distribution, but the uniform one was chosen for the comparison of the results. Indeed, the Gaussian distribution for example is too dependent on the random generation especially for the long baseline. Using an uniform distribution enable to have trust in the the resolution given by the formula $res = \frac{\lambda}{D_{max}}$ in every direction for each generation - although, a uniform distribution on a sphere would be more accurate -. A representation of this distribution is showed on figure 6.1.

I used a central wavelength of $\nu = 30kHz$ which corresponds to a wavelength $\lambda = 10km$ and hence a resolution of $\frac{\lambda}{D_{max}} = 5.7^\circ$. There are three reasons in using such a low frequency. First, the interferometer is meant to be able to image the sky at this frequency. Second, this low resolution allows to work with an image with a less pixels and thus to have a faster computation time. Third, the Point Spread Function (PSF) of the main source is large at this frequency and enables an easier interpretation of the output images. For the second part of the pipeline, a higher frequency $\nu_{hf} = 240kHz$ was used. In practice the frequency used for this function should be chosen higher, however, the ratio between the two resolutions should remain similar no matter the frequency. Indeed, if the high frequency is set too high, it increases the chance for the least square fit to find a local maxima that is not the source being tracked. This frequency ratio is thus a trade-off between angular precision and consistency. The high frequency gives a resolution of 0.7° but the fitting function enables to get a sub-pixel precision on the position of the sources.

The output images are Healpix map [10]. The idea behind these maps is that the pixels are evenly distributed around the sphere and all of them covers the same area. It

Figure 6.1: Satellite positions in the simulation

also has the advantages that the pixels are isolatitude, which makes the computation of spherical harmonics easier. These maps are defined by their number of side that verifies $N_{pix} = 12N_{side}^2$ and N_{side} can only be choose as a power of 2. It was set to $N_{side} = 2^6$ for the low frequency and $N_{side} = 2^{10}$ for the high frequency.

In order to display the maps, the Mollweide projection was used as for a planisphere.

6.2 Signal simulation

Data In the first place, in order to simulate the sky, I made a random distribution of point sources with random intensities. However, the sky at low frequencies is dominated by a small number of bright sources. This means that the radio source tracker is highly relying on the position of those sources, which means that the simulations have to be run with a realistic sky. For that, I used the best map I could find covering the whole sky at the lowest frequencies. I used the map from the Global Sky Model (GSM 2008) at 50 MHz [11] and also a list of the point sources at the same frequency provided by the LOFAR database [12]. Although, the amplitude should change with the frequency, this only matters when two frequencies are used in the deconvolution algorithm. As the difference in brightness is supposed to be modeled by a power law, the problem is avoided. That is why the same data were used map to compute the signal for every frequency in this simulation.

Also, the activity of a powerful source like the Sun or Jupiter can have a major influence on the efficiency of the radio source tracker so it must be taken in account. It was chosen to simulate this with an extra point source whose brightness and position can be selected by the operator.

In order to simulate the signal received on the antennas, the simulation decomposes the signal from different origins. The signal coming from point sources, the signal coming from diffuse emission and the one coming from specific object like the Sun or Jupiter. $A = A_{point\ sources} + A_{continuum} + A_{sun}$ and $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_{point\ sources} + \mathcal{V}_{continuum} + \mathcal{V}_{sun}$.

However, the GSM map is already composed of the signals coming from both the continuum and the point sources with a complex PSF related to the GSM building process. Thus, the point sources from this map were removed. To do so, a disc is selected around these sources and the value of the pixels inside is set to the average value of the surrounding pixels.

Point sources In order to be realistic, one can simulate a random signal coming from each sources and select the time interval that each satellite receive during the snapshot and compute the time average later on. However, this approach is not necessarily in the scope of this internship and way too computationally costing. Instead, I used the results from chapter 4.

I used the formula 4.2 and 4.5 with $E_s(t) = E_s e^{i c \phi_s}$ where E_s is the electric field coming from the source s and ϕ_s a random phase.

Continuum In order to deal with the continuum, it was chosen to discretize the sky and consider each element as a point source. Indeed, if one consider a portion of the sky small enough for $B(\Omega_k)$ and the phase shift to be consider constant, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} A_i &= \int_{\theta-\Delta\theta/2}^{\theta+\Delta\theta/2} \int_{\phi-\Delta\phi/2}^{\phi+\Delta\phi/2} E(\theta', \phi') \exp(-i_c \vec{k}(\theta', \phi') \cdot \vec{X}_i) \cos(\theta') d\theta' d\phi' \\ &\simeq B(\theta, \phi) \exp(-i_c \vec{k}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \vec{X}_i) dS \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

with $dS = \int_{\theta-\Delta\theta/2}^{\theta+\Delta\theta/2} \cos(\theta') d\theta' d\phi'$ the surface of the element.

In order for this approximation to be relevant, it is necessary to choose a discretization step smaller than the resolution of the interferometer at a given frequency. As the resolution is 0.7° at the high frequency, a discretization step 4 times smaller $\sim 0.2^\circ$ was chosen. In practice, a highly resolved healpix map is used. The simulation reduces its resolution to the one required and then considers it as a large list of point sources.

As every element that emits signal is considered as a point source, the equations become linear for both the individual signals and the visibilities.

6.3 Metrics

In order to qualify the results of the simulation it is necessary to choose a metric that quantify the efficiency of the method.

Image For the images, one criteria that can be used is the intensity of the residual. As the PSF of a source is spread all over the image, one can measure its average amplitude. Although, the PSF is determined by the current topology of the swarm, it can be deteriorated by the imaging method.

To do so, the different imaging algorithms were tested for the same swarm topology with only two point sources at the same places. Then, a mask is generated around the sources with a radius equals to two times the resolution. And finally, the images are normalized and the average and the standard deviation σ is computed on the rest of the image.

It was chosen to work with two sources instead of one because the coherent sum and the DFT method both give the same map if one uses only one point source. Using two enables to highlight the differences between these methods.

Rotation What matters for the rotation is its ability to place a point from the system frame to its actual position in the absolute frame. The simulation rotate the sky thanks to a quaternion $M_{rot,0}$ and then compute a quaternion $M_{rot,mes}$. Although, the two quaternions can be compared using the Euclidean norm of their difference, this information is not linked to the angular precision. Instead, the same vector \vec{s} is applied to both rotation and its angular distance is measured. $err = angle(M_{rot,0}\vec{s}, M_{rot,mes}\vec{s})$ Of course, one vector is not enough to qualify the precision, so I used a Monte-Carlo method: this angular error is computed for a large set of vectors uniformly distributed over the celestial sphere. A set of a 100 vectors were used and their angular error was averaged.

Chapter 7

Results

7.1 Imaging algorithm

In the first place all algorithms were able to reconstruct an image of the sky as depicted in figure 7.1. Yet, the beamforming method showed a significantly worst performance compared to the others and can be seen with the eye.

To compute the metric for the SWHT method, we were limited by computation capacity and could not reconstruct an image while using polar number l_{max} higher than 85. Thus, the metric was evaluated for a frequency of 8 kHz in order to match the resolution of the SWHT method. The intensity of the two sources was chosen equals to 1 in order to normalize the images. Hence the results are expressed in percent of the amplitude of the sources. The metric was also evaluated for 30 kHz, but the quantal number is also set to $l_{max} = 85$. The results are shown in table 7.1.

The evaluation with the metric gives a better performance for the beamforming method but can be explained by the small number of sources and the lack of the implementation of the continuum. On the other hand, it requires very few computational

Method	beamforming	DFT	SWHT
8 kHz			
Metric average	3.40%	3.84%	4.09%
Metric σ	3.13%	2.60%	4.86%
30 kHz			
Metric average	3.99%	3.96%	4.41%
Metric σ	3.92%	2.72%	3.09%
Complexity	$\mathcal{O}(N_{sat}N_{pix})$	$\mathcal{O}(N_{sat}^2N_{pix})$	$\mathcal{O}((N_{pix}/\pi)^{3/2}\log((N_{pix}/\pi)^{3/2}))$
Deconvolution	yes	yes	unknown

Table 7.1: Comparison of the imaging methods

Figure 7.1: Image reconstruction with different methods at $\nu = 30kHz$: (a) Beamforming, (b) DFT and (c) SWHT

resources. Thereby, this technique is easy to implement and a deconvolution can easily be computed with it. Nethertheless, for the second part of the pipeline, the algorithms were not able to find more than two sources which is not enough to compute the rotation matrix. Thus, this imaging method was not selected for our purpose.

The Spherical Wave Harmonic Transform method demonstrated its performance to reconstruct an image similar to the one with the DFT. However, the metric highlighted that the point spread function (PSF) is less reliable when using this methods. One has to keep in mind that its evaluation with the metric could be better if the polar number l_{max} were to be greater. Furthermore, no method has been developed in order to run a deconvolution with this method and it might be impossible to do so. This lack of deconvolution combined with its need for a high computational capacity have led us to drop this method for now.

Thereby, the Discrete Fourier Transform method has been chosen through this internship. It combined the advantage of being relatively easy to compute because it can be highly parallelized, and the advantage of being able to run a deconvolution and it reconstructs images nicely as the metric shows. Indeed, although the average of the PSF is not the best, it has the lowest standard deviation σ which means the PSF is closer to an offset outside of the source position, thus there are less chance to confuse it with another source.

7.2 Orientation measurement

The orientation error have evaluated in regards to different factors of influence:

- The error on the satellite position
- The brightness of the Sun
- The amplitude of the noise
- The frequencies used to find the sources

The results were computed for $\nu = 30$ kHz and are shown in the following tables:

satellite position error (m)	0	0.1	1	10	100
orientation error (arcmin)	0.372	0.375	0.376	0.370	0.373

Table 7.2: Impact on the orientation measurement of the error on the satellite position

Sun amplitude (Jy)	0	10^4	10^5	10^6	5.10^6
orientation error (arcmin)	0.372	0.383	0.344	1.019	no pattern-match

Table 7.3: Impact on the orientation measurement of the brightness of the Sun

Noise amplitude (in equivalent Jy)	0	10	100	1.000	5.000	10.000	20.000
orientation error (arcmin)	0.372	0.374	0.360	0.388	0.445	0.571	0.784

Table 7.4: Impact on the orientation measurement of the noise level

Frequencies (kHz)	10/80	30/240	50/400	100/800
orientation error (arcmin)	no sources found	0.372	0.363	0.236

Table 7.5: Impact on the orientation measurement of frequencies used

The error on the satellite position shows no real impact on the precision of the measure. For a too high error, the pipeline was not able to retrieve an orientation because not enough sources were found in the image.

The presence of the Sun is an exception because as the position of the Sun is known it can be added to the catalog in order to use its position as another reference point. Thus, if the Sun has a brightness similar to the one of the A-team, the precision gets better. However for a greater brightness, the features of the PSF of the Sun makes the algorithm to make a lot of false detection making it impossible to measure the orientation.

The noise amplitude coming from the antenna’s temperature is already known and is around $3 - 5nV/Hz$. However, at very low frequency, the dominant noise is the quasi-thermal noise or the galactic background [13]. Also, the simulated brightness of the sources correspond to those at 50 MHz and cannot be compared to the brightness of the noise at a few kHz. Thus, a noise equivalent in Jy was added to the signal for a large range of amplitude. The results shows that the noise has a negligible impact below 1000 Jy but the precision starts to decrease with the noise afterwards. At 20000 Jy, the noise level is equivalent to the brightness of the A-team and thus the signal to noise ratio is close to 1 and still the orientation can be retrieved.

The impact of the frequency is as expected: the higher the frequency — and thus the resolution — used the higher the precision on the measurement.

What comes out of this measurement is that most of the sources of noise do not impact the precision on the orientation much but do degrade the quality of the images reconstructed and thus makes it hard for the second part of the pipeline to retrieve the sources position. In most cases the algorithm was limited by the number of found sources instead of the precision on their position. This can be explained by the criteria applied on the gaussian function that fitted to the image. This criteria might have to be set in regards to the errors involved.

Still, all measurement achieved a precision better than 1 arcmin. In regards to the scientific objectives, one can be optimistic for the project. It should be able to cover a large variety of scientific topics or at least should not be constraint by the orientation measurement.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

8.1 Science

All in all, this internship has led to conclude that a radio source tracker is a viable solution for the interferometer to retrieve its orientation. The simulations, in spite of their defaults, give encouraging results for this solution. It seems that a precision under 1 arcmin can be achieved, which is reassuring regarding the scientific objectives.

On the other hand, this work has raised new issues in the project. Although, the orientation can be retrieved in LIS mode, the tracking mode has not been developed yet. Also, the processing time is concerning. Indeed, if the interferometer takes too much time to switch to the tracking mode, it might not be able to find the sources where it expects them to be as the orientation of the system evolves with the swarm topology. Thereby, the computation capability of the interferometer and the optimization of the algorithm are issues that need to be addressed in the future.

Another issue raised through this work is the imaging capability of the instrument. The use of deconvolution seems inevitable, as the reconstructed images of the sky have shown to be dominated by the brightest bodies no matter the direction. This is due to the point spread function induced by the swarm topology and no imaging method is immune to this. It can also be explained by the fact that the interferometer's antennas are receiving signal from the whole sky. The deconvolution is a major concern. If this process were to be done aboard the satellites, it would require a significant computation power and it is unlikely that this computation can be distributed across the satellites.

8.2 Further work

Despite its promising results, the simulation part would benefit from various improvements in order to reduce the number of hypothesis and get closer to a realistic instrument. The simulation is able to simulate the three dipole antennas per sensor node

and run with polarization measurement. However, this simulation is not presented in this report as a polarized map of the sky requires to run it and no result have been produced yet with it.

Also, the tracking mode is yet to be developed and the simulation can be upgraded to test it in various conditions especially for the rotation speed of the system's orientation.

Furthermore, the simulation would benefit from using more realistic conditions. For instance, in a future update the Sun would be simulated as an extended source. Also, the simulation of the received signals should be done with a more resolved map of the sky. This might require to take advantage of greater computation unit.

Another improvement that should be made in a future work, would be to improve the error estimation. Other sources of error should be explored like the synchronization of the clock or the error on the orientation of the antennas. Also, the result presented in the previous chapter were computed with the same swarm topology and rotation of the sky. However it would be more accurate, to average the error over a set of random topologies and rotations.

Once the simulations are sufficiently precise for the purpose of the project, it would be possible to estimate of computation power needed aboard the satellites. This factor could have an impact on the design of the satellites and also on the way the interferometer distributes computation. It would also be possible to draw conclusions in regards to the scientific objectives with more confidence.

8.3 Personal conclusion

This internship has been a nice opportunity for me to get involved in the early development of a scientific space mission. I had the pleasure to work with a very qualified team and a great understanding of the underlying process in radio astronomy. I was able to make good use of the skills I acquired throughout my education in space engineering on a concrete project that I value.

I like this project very much and I am planning on continuing this work at LESIA in the years to come. NOIRE promises to get a greater understanding of the phenomena taking place on other celestial bodies. The idea that a further knowledge of the Dark Ages might be achievable is very rousing. Moreover, this project could make improvement in engineering on computation distribution for instance. One thing I like about it, also, is the fact that the instrument itself is composed of different sensor unit and it is only by considering all the pieces together that the instrument exists. Each individual satellite is completely unable to generate an image contrarily to them as a group.

Appendix A

Formula

The visibility is expressed in equation 4.4 as:

$$\mathcal{V}(u, v, w) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} B(l, m) e^{-2i_c \pi [ul + vm + w\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}]} \frac{dl dm}{\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}}$$

By applying the inverse Fourier transform, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} F(l, m, n) &= \iiint \mathcal{V}(u, v, w) e^{2i_c \pi [ul + vm + wn]} du dv dw \\ &= \iint \left\{ \iiint B(l', m') e^{-2i_c \pi [ul' + vm' + w\sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2}]} \frac{dl' dm'}{\sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. e^{2i_c \pi [ul + vm + wn]} du dv dw \right. \\ &= \iiint \left\{ \iint B(l', m') e^{-2i_c \pi u(l-l')} e^{-2i_c \pi v(m-m')} \right. \\ &\quad \left. e^{-2i_c \pi w(n - \sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2})} du dv dw \right\} \frac{dl' dm'}{\sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2}} \\ &= \iint B(l', m') \delta(l-l') \delta(m-m') \delta(n - \sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2}) \frac{dl' dm'}{\sqrt{1-l'^2-m'^2}} \\ &= B(l, m) \frac{\delta(n - \sqrt{1-l^2-m^2})}{\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}} \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

with

$$\delta(l-l') = \int e^{-2i_c \pi u(l-l')} du$$

Bibliography

- [1] Baptiste Cecconi, Moustapha Dekkali, Carine Briand, Boris Segret, Julien N. Girard, Andre Laurens, Alain Lamy, David Valat, Michel Delpech, Mickael Bruno, and et al. Noire study report: Towards a low frequency radio interferometer in space. *2018 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, Mar 2018.
- [2] Justin Kasper, Joseph Lazio, Andrew Romero-Wolf, James Lux, Tim Neilsen, and null. The sun radio interferometer space experiment (sunrise) mission concept. pages 1–12, 2020.
- [3] Alfredo Renga and Antonio Moccia. Moon-based synthetic aperture radar: Review and challenges. pages 3708–3711, 2016.
- [4] WC Erickson RM Manning Dulk GA and Jean-Louis Bougeret. Calibration of Low-Frequency Radio Telescopes Using the Galactic Background Radiation. *Astrophys*, 365:294–300, 2001.
- [5] RM Manning and GA Dulk. The Galactic Background Radiation From 0.2 to 13.8 MHz. *Astrophys*, 372:663–66, 2001.
- [6] C. L. Carilli G. B. Taylor and R. A. Perley. Synthesis imaging in radio astronomy ii. *A Collection of Lectures from the Sixth NRAO/NMIMT Synthesis Imaging Summer School*, 180, 1999.
- [7] T. D. Carozzi and G. Woan. A generalized measurement equation and van Cittert-Zernike theorem for wide-field radio astronomical interferometry. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 395(3):1558–1568, 05 2009.
- [8] T. D. Carozzi. Imaging on a sphere with interferometers: the spherical wave harmonic transform. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters*, 451(1):L6–L10, 05 2015.
- [9] Edward J. Groth. A pattern-matching algorithm for two-dimensional coordinate lists. *The astronomical journal*, 91, may 1986.

- [10] K. M. Gorski, E. Hivon, A. J. Banday, B. D. Wandelt, F. K. Hansen, M. Reinecke, and M. Bartelmann. HEALPix: A framework for high-resolution discretization and fast analysis of data distributed on the sphere. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 622(2):759–771, apr 2005.
- [11] B. M. Gaensler J. Jonas T. L. Landecker P. Reich A. De Oliveira-Costa, M. Tegmark. A model of diffuse Galactic radio emission from 10 MHz to 100 GHz. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 388, July 2008.
- [12] Lofar <<https://lcs165.lofar.eu/>>.
- [13] R. Prangé W. S. Kurth P. Louarn B. Cecconi L. Lamy P. Zarka. Goniopolarimetric study of the revolution 29 perikrone using the Cassini Radio and Plasma Wave Science instrument high-frequency radio receiver. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 114, march 2011.

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